

Notes

Volumetric Determination of Cinnamic Acid by Oxidation with Aqueous Iodine Catalysed by Mercuric Salts

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SEVERAL workers¹⁻⁴ have determined cinnamic acid by various physico-chemical and chemical methods. Iodine solution in the presence of mercuric salts have been used as a titrimetric reagent by various workers^{5,6}.

The present workers used the procedure⁶ which involved a mixture of aqueous iodine and mercuric salts solutions for the determination of cinnamate.

Stock solutions of cinnamic acid, iodine and mercuric salts of A.R. (B.D.H.) grade were prepared in double distilled water. A solution of cinnamic acid or its salts containing 0.5 to 14 mg of it was

taken in iodine flask and treated with a known excess of standard aqueous iodine solution. To this mixture a required amount of mercuric chloride was added and it was allowed to stand for three minutes at room temperature. Later the mixture was treated with 5 ml. of 4N H₂SO₄ and 0.5 g of potassium iodide and the residual iodine was titrated with a standard solution of thiosulphate using starch solution as indicator. The amount of cinnamic acid can be calculated from the equation :

The role played by mercuric chloride in this reaction may probably be the same as suggested by Giuseppe Scotti⁶ in the determination of iodine value of oils and fats. The results are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Effect of concentration of Mercuric Salts : There is almost no reaction between cinnamic acid and aqueous iodine in the absence of mercuric salts. A large excess of mercuric salt affects the results.

TABLE 1. DETERMINATION OF CINNAMIC ACID
Time—3 min.

Sl. No.	Iodine solution taken 0.0023N ml	HgCl ₂ added 0.01M ml	Hypo. required of 0.01N ml	Iodine-consumed as 0.01N ml	Cinnamic acid		% Error
					taken mg.	found mg.	
1.	25.0	—	5.85*	—	—	—	—
2.	-do-	3.0	5.20	0.65	0.47	0.48	+ 2.0
3.	-do-	-do-	4.62	1.23	0.88	0.90	+ 2.27
4.	-do-	-do-	4.25	1.60	1.18	1.18	Nil
5.	100.0	—	23.40*	—	—	—	—
6.	-do-	25.0	16.81	6.50	4.88	4.87	+ 0.20
7.	-do-	-do-	10.16	13.24	9.76	9.80	+ 0.40
8.	-do-	-do-	6.91	16.49	12.20	12.20	Nil
9.	-do-	-do-	3.58	19.82	14.64	14.67	+ 0.20
10.	-do-	Nil	23.39	0.01	9.76	0.01	-99.9
11.	-do-	Nil	23.38	0.02	14.64	0.01	-99.9

* Blank reading in terms of 0.01N Hypo.

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TABLE 2. DETERMINATION OF SODIUM CINNAMATE
Time—3 min.

Sl. No.	Mercuric chloride of 0.01M added = 25 ml.			Sodium cinnamate		% Error
	Iodine solution taken 0.0023N ml	Hypo. of 0.01N ml	Iodine consumed as 0.01N ml	Taken mg.	Found mg.	
1.	100.0	23.40*	--	--	--	
2.	-do-	17.00	6.40	5.44	5.46	+0.36
3.	-do-	13.78	9.62	8.16	8.16	Nil
4.	-do-	10.53	12.87	10.88	10.92	+0.36
5.	-do-	7.38	16.02	13.60	13.61	+0.07

* Blank reading in terms of 0.01N Hypo.

Effect of Iodide Ions : The effect of iodide ion concentration on reaction was studied. It is observed that the reaction is incomplete in 3 minutes time in the presence of iodide ions and hence low results are afforded for cinnamic acid.

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Spectrophotometric Studies of the Chelates of Iron(III) : 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone thiosemicarbazone System

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SALICYLALDEHYDE and 2-hydroxyphenones offer an interesting field of study as reagents for spectrophotometric studies of iron(III)¹⁻⁸. The chelating tendencies of salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone have been studied by various workers⁹⁻¹¹, however, the analytical potentialities of 2-hydroxyphenone thiosemicarbazones have not been investigated fully. The present paper reports the results of spectrophotometric studies of the green coloured solution formed when iron(III) salts react with alcoholic solution of the 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone thiosemicarbazone (5MeOATS).

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-5-Methyl acetophenone (5MeOHA) was prepared as described earlier¹². The 5MeOATS was obtained as yellow crystals by refluxing the 1:1 note of 5MeOHA and thiosemicarbazide in methanol for 1½ hr. The product was purified by recrystallization from acetic acid. The standard solutions, temperature, medium, absorbance and pH measurements were made as described earlier⁷.

Results and Discussion

The nature of the complexes was determined by the method of Vosburgh and Cooper¹³. Only one complex with $\lambda_{max} = 645$ nm is formed under the conditions employed (pH \approx 2.0). The 1:1 composition of the complex was determined by Job's method¹⁴ using equimolar and non equimolar metal and reagent solutions, the Slope ratio method¹⁵, and mole-ratio method. It was found that concentration of HNO₃ had a marked effect on the colour intensity of the complex.

The apparent stability constant of the complex log K = 4.0 ± 0.1 was calculated by the method of Mukherji and Dey¹⁷.

Beer's law : A series of solutions, each with a pH = 2.2 and containing the same concentration (5 × 10⁻⁴ M) of the reagent but varying (from 5 × 10⁻⁶ M to 2 × 10⁻⁴ M) concentration of iron(III) were prepared and their absorbances were measured at 645 nm. The results show that Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.5 to 8 µg iron(III) per ml.

Effect of diverse ions : The interference due to diverse metal ions on the colour intensity of the complex was studied and the results are summarized in the following table.

TABLE		
Foreign ion	Added as	Tolerance limit µg/100 ml
VO ⁺⁺	VOSO ₄ .H ₂ O	None
Cu ⁺⁺	CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O	None
Zn ⁺⁺	Zn(ClO ₄) ₂ .6H ₂ O	1000
Co ⁺⁺	Co(ClO ₄) ₂ .6H ₂ O	850
Mn ⁺⁺	Mn(ClO ₄) ₂ .6H ₂ O	800
Ni ⁺⁺	Ni(NO ₃) ₂ .6H ₂ O	850

Determination of the composition of complexes of iron(III) with oxalate and EDTA by equilibrium with coloured Fe(5MeOATS)⁺² complex in isomolar series :

The method is similar to the one described earlier¹⁸⁻²⁰. The coloured solution of Fe(5MeOATS)⁺² (1 × 10⁻⁴ M) was prepared by mixing equal volumes of iron(III) (2 × 10⁻⁴ M) and 5MeOHATS (1 × 10⁻³ M) solutions. (acidity w.r.t. HNO₃ is \sim 1 × 10⁻² M). A series of mixtures was then prepared using Fe(5MeOATS)⁺² (1 × 10⁻⁴ M) and Na₂EDTA/ammonium